

Transaction

Developed by: Center für Lehr- und Lernservices, RWTH Aachen University

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Keywords

Business, Economics, Logistics, Production Planning, Strategic Decision-making, Systems Thinking

Introduction

Transaction is a web- and browser-based business simulation that began development in 2014. It was designed to offer bachelor's students in business administration and industrial engineering the opportunity to participate in a value chain throughout an entire semester actively. Participants act as executives of a virtual company and improve their game performance by applying the knowledge they have acquired during their studies. All actions within the simulation are automatically recorded and evaluated, providing students with continuous, individual feedback on their learning progress.

Facts

Release date:	First used in 2014, continuously developed
Developer:	Center für Lehr- und Lernservices (CLS)
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Scalable
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	Around one hour per week
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Laptop, PC, or mobile device with internet access
Material:	All required materials are included in the game or provided through the accompanying course
Price:	Part of the CLS service offering at RWTH Aachen University; licensing for external universities is available

Resonance & Criticism

Student feedback has been predominantly positive. In surveys, 80% reported that the simulation improved their understanding of the lecture content. Only a few participants expressed criticism regarding its integration into face-to-face teaching, while many wanted to see it expanded to additional courses. *Transaction* is perceived not as a mere computer game

but as a serious, exam-relevant challenge. Conscious and reflective decision-making intensifies the learning process. At present, only internal evaluations are available; no scientific studies on effectiveness have yet been published.

Game principle & Process

Figure 1. Screenshot from Transaction (RWTH Aachen University) showing a drag-and-drop accounting task in which players assign balance sheet components to their correct positions. Screenshot taken from a video tutorial published by RWTH Aachen University. Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Transaction is a digital serious game in which participants take over the management of a virtual car factory and must lead it to success through economically sound decisions. The game spans an entire semester, with one game round completed each week. In each round, students go through the whole production cycle of an automobile and handle all related management tasks. These include determining production quantities within production planning, procuring required parts and materials, and hiring qualified staff. In addition, participants sell components and finished products under the best possible market conditions. Furthermore, they support computer-generated colleagues in solving business-related problems within the company (see Figure 1). Through this holistic structure, students realistically experience operational interdependencies and gain a deeper understanding of how different business areas are interconnected.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The primary objective of Transaction is to promote and sustainably anchor a comprehensive business-oriented way of thinking and acting among students. The simulation conveys an in-

depth understanding of key business relationships, particularly regarding cost structures, opportunities for efficiency, and the economic effects of different batch sizes and production decisions. Students learn how operational decisions have direct and indirect impacts on costs, revenues, and a company's competitiveness.

In addition, Transaction specifically strengthens strategic decision-making skills by enabling participants to independently develop business strategies, make market decisions, and continuously adapt them throughout the simulation. A particular focus is placed on applying theoretical content to practice-oriented problem situations: Concepts taught in lectures are implemented directly within the virtual company, and their consequences are systematically reflected upon. In this way, the transfer of theoretical knowledge into practical competence is promoted. The simulation is completed independently by students as self-directed work; continuous supervision is not required.

Effectiveness

Since its introduction, the Transaction simulation has been used by more than 80,000 students and has become an integral component of bachelor's-level teaching at RWTH Aachen University. It is employed in several courses, each tailored to specific learning objectives.

In the courses "Production and Logistics" and "Marketing – Sales and Procurement," a self-directed learning concept is emphasized, with varying content priorities. The simulation runs throughout the entire semester, allowing students to review learned content and deepen their understanding without in-class discussions.

In the course "Introduction to Business Administration," Transaction is an integral part of a blended-learning concept using a flipped-classroom format. Video tutorials are integrated directly into the business simulation game, and students address current issues from the lecture each week in the context of their virtual company. In addition, modified versions of the simulation exist for courses on operational accounting.

Regardless of the application concept, the simulation can account for up to 30 percent of the final semester grade. The assessment is based on the students' problem-solving skills and the overall economic success of their virtual company.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Despite its success, there are challenges to consider in the game's further development. Some mechanics have been deliberately simplified to focus clearly on key learning objectives, but this can lead to repetitive processes. In addition, the simulation completely dispenses with random events such as supplier failures or price fluctuations. While this ensures fair assessment in an exam context, it only reflects the dynamics of fundamental markets to a limited extent. Furthermore, Transaction does not automatically account for differences in

students' prior knowledge, which can leave them under- or overchallenged depending on their individual experiences.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Johannes Christian Mieth

Sources

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